

Interview Biscarrosse, Sylvie Bergès et Ursula Maurer
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WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys_ Guidelines for interviews.

- Presentation of the museum

The Musée de l'Hydravion in Biscarrosse is a municipal museum with Label Musée de France since 2002.

Created in 1982 by an association under municipal tutelage, to tell local history + seaplane history at the international level. Unique museum in Europe on this theme, 1 other ex, but more local, in Ireland. The Association of Museum Friends is still there, mainly older members, but new recruits since 2018. Museum located on historical site by the Biscarrosse lake, where the Latécoère seaplane assembly base was settled previously.

Golden age of seaplanes until the end of the 30 years: Aeropostale, Ocean Liners. There were main lines and smaller lines, a little more experimental. Rich local past but with national and international implications.

Before the WWII, Biscarrosse was the only hydro base in France. Guillemet, Saint-Exupéry: associated with important men, historical figures.

Biscarrosse was European hub for seaplanes.

Another project before the war: construction of an international airport, but not completed.

In 80 and 81: 2 whole German planes were recovered from the lake (Dorniers 24), exhibited outside, began to degrade. Museum was created at the same time. There was also a big exhibition/meeting for the centenary of Latécoère. These 2 aircrafts were meant to be donated to the Museum's association, but it was not formalized until 2002. In the meantime they were kept by a private person at his home in Bordeaux.

In the 90's, the Museum was a sponsoring lab in treatment for Al alloys, working with C. Degryny and Valectra foundation. Work on seaplanes from the lake. Electrochemical treatment on various objects, still in good condition today. It was not possible to continue/train someone in the long term after C. Degryny left. A bit sporadic at the beginning with volunteers who had skills.

In 98, renewed contact with Arc Antique (about 17th century guns) which is continued through Procraft.

- The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved ? Defining a recovery project? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing ? What is their approach? Is it similar or different approach if different projects ?

Airplanes in 80's was a fortuitous discovery. Subsequently, excavations have continued to recover objects.

Divers from the General armament antenna for missile tests are stationed nearby. To train they dive into the lake and inform the museum of what is at the bottom of the lake. Recovery process is mainly based volunteers and personal will, no formal partnership between the 2 institutions. Excavations in the 90's, questions following the unfortunate experience of German 80's aircraft.

Today, continued links with military divers, identification of pieces but they are left in the water. Museum is involved from the beginning of projects and at all stages.

Significant legal concerns about these 2 aircrafts recovered in the 80's.

Before Procraft, the Museum was not aware they needed to get permission of the owner of the land/lake to take in the aircrafts.

Therefore, they have not accepted to integrate these 2 aircrafts in the Procraft corpus to avoid making waves, as they are afraid to loose them.

Did not know before the permission of the owner of the land / lake before Procraft

They also receive repeated requests from German associations, who need original parts to have government subsidies to rebuild historical aircraft. The museum does not answer for the moment.

Another significant legal concern regards the rules the museum is supposed to follow for recovery/ownership of wrecks. As they are situated on a lake, they are not subject to the DRASSM regulation (which covers maritime domain), but are not yet sure they are submitted the DRAC regulations (land). Big legal concern for them.

Next projects: they will give better attention to administrative framework.

- Concept of "conservation": Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle? How do you define long term? What does the idea of "conservation" mean to you for this kind of heritage ? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations ? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution ?

Today the Dornier aircrafts have turned to pieces, because of very advanced degradation.

Initially they very preserved. Freshwater lake and lots of mud = excellent state of conservation. But have degraded a lot since they came out, very degraded today.

Primary concern today is the conservation of materials, try to stabilize the current state. There is not even concern about presentation. Also there is not enough space to put them in the exhibition spaces. There is a project for a larger museum in the next 7-10 years.

The museum would like to reintegrate these forgotten seaplanes into the museographic discourse. The current scenography considered is to present them as lying at the bottom of the lake.

Generally speaking, museum has a rather "archeological" bias: they wish to preserve as much as possible the integrity of their pieces as they have arrived. But for the Dorniers, the current degraded condition requires to ask unforeseen questions and perhaps choose different treatments of parts depending on materials / condition.

In the next 3 years, the museum will see a renewal of the exhibition spaces, oriented more towards scientific and technical approach. Also wish to attract visitor's attention aeronautical archaeology.

- Who works on these collections (after recovery) : conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration?

Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly ? (addition to Form A)

No direct intervention today on WWII parts. Just monitoring.

Interventions on other collections, difference of treatment according to the materials concerned.

Example of an American aircraft (about 25m wingspan) that participated in the Korean War (1950-1953). American plane, but bought by Italy, still in flying condition in the 80s. Good condition when arrived in Biscarrosse. Restored through a "Qualification Nouvelle Chance" project: to train 30 jobseekers in aeronautical skills.

The approach was mainly refecton of parts. Work with the same methods as during the construction, except for painting with choice to return to the American livery. Pieces supplied form the US, indication on plan of new elements added or remade.

Differences in choices of treatment for this aircraft: role of aeronautical conservator only recently started to get a bit more structure. Museum has contact with MAE (Le Bourget, France) and Arnaud Mars before starting restoration. This decision was taken because this aircraft has been produced in very large number of copies, many of them still in flying condition, is not a unicum at the moment.

Presentation to the visitor of the active life of this aircraft during Korean War, along with mediation to explain history around it.

Today this aircraft is kept in outdoors, in saline atmosphere, degrades significantly.
(Form A to be completed for coreen aircraft).

Not the same approach for Dorniers, because they are much more rare.

Teams working more generally on the collections : volunteers, 1 graduate conservator retired 10 years ago but not replaced.

2012 to 2018: no one qualified to make interventions on the collections. Volunteers don't always have all the technical skills and the understanding of the ethical framework (general desire is to bring everything to new condition).

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact : aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage /outdoors (addition to Form A) ?

Musée de l'Hydraviation is not a flying museum at all. Have recently acquired a 1947 aircraft, in flight condition, but will not fly.

Deliberate choice of static display. Seaplane aviation period is quite short, a few decades.

Question arose to have a flying aircraft to present in meetings, but decisions has not been carried out. It would be too heavy to manage for associative museum: requires a specific place, an experienced pilot, technical skills to avoid damages.

It is also complicated to increase the collection, as most sea aircrafts are in the USA. The priority is to show the maximum to visitors, which is easier with static devices.

Also very restrictive regulations to obtain the necessary certifications for a flying historical aircraft.

Perhaps this decision could evolve with future museum.

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage) : rooms or hall ? awareness about influence of climate on preservation ? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A) ?

5 different spaces for storage, generally poor storage conditions :

- majority of the aircrafts are in a 400 m² shed, made of sheet metal with a glass façade, exposed West. No HR/Temp control, very strong variations are perceptible but no reports. Great variety of materials, seem to withstand rather well these conditions. Main problem is light and sun. A lot of dust and birds. Some WWII parts in this hangar.
- another part of WWII artefacts are sheltered under a canvas open tent, facing East & West winds, protects from North & South winds
- Museum spaces, with HR /Temp control. Small WWII pieces exhibited in the museum.

Readings are expected

- other space of storage with regular reports for climate.
- and still other external storage area belonging to a private person, without climate control, closed space, but quite remote. Implementation of climate control is planned.

“No significant degradation”: In fact, Sylvie and Ursula both agree it is difficult to evaluate the degradation and its evolution.

No control of pollutants in any of the storage/display spaces.

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems) ? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks ? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant)? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A)?

There is no observed change in condition for all artefacts previously treated with electrochemistry. Degradation is mainly observed for artefacts kept outdoors. Beyond Al alloys, significant problems with Fe alloys.

WWII parts kept outdoors have not received electrochemical treatment or other special treatment.

It is not always possible to determine the reasons for the degradation of the pieces outdoors.

- Reflecting on their own practice : do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts ? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about ? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field ? Has your practice evolved through those connections?

Would reuse electrochemical treatments, satisfied with the results. But maybe it is not really required, rinsing could be enough.

They try to keep up with conservation practices elsewhere, France and abroad.

Hope that Project Procraft will be able to provide answers to unresolved questions. They would also like information on appropriate restoration products and practices.

Would you like to continue research on the subject with Procraft. Would also like to integrate more projects such as Procraft and research generally. But as there is no position for a heritage scientist at the museum, Sylvie & Ursula cannot commit more than 10% of their working time.

For a long time museum has focused on aesthetics, new appearance, "pleasure of the eyes". They realized it was not the best approach, the team of the museum is now choosing a more scientific approach, and wish to keep as much as possibly integrity of the original materials. Don't really know what the visitors think about this new orientation.

Issues with finding skills as an aeronautical conservator.

Connections with aeronautical high-schools to train young people.

Try to get the right contacts, but problems to find skills or refernces, especially bibliographic.

Also problems to train curators. Contacts with Aeroscopia. Contacts abroad more on the mediation part, less on the technical part. Language barrier too. Lack of internal skills on purely technical subjects.

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history ?

They feel there is a need to connect the preservation of aeronautical heritage to the preservation of industrial heritage as a broader field.